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Understanding the Performance of Ground Motion Models in Megathrust Tectonic Environments

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Understanding the Performance of Ground Motion Models in Megathrust Tectonic Environments

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MOTIVATION AND PROJECT OVERVIEW

A common approach for estimating earthquake ground motions (GMs), and a key component within seismic hazard assessments is using ergodic ground motion models (GMMs) that account for the contributions of the earthquake source, the travel path, and local geologic conditions on GM characteristics. Despite their broad usage in engineering practice, ergodic GMMs are developed based on global data and thus, they cannot fully capture systematic patterns in specific areas of interest. This issue becomes particularly important for applications in data-scarce regions such as the Cascadia Subduction Zone (CSZ) in the US Pacific Northwest. The main goal of this project is to assess the extent to which selected GMMs provide accurate estimates of median GMs and their associated variability in the megathrust tectonic environments. Selected GMMs will be evaluated using three complementary approaches, including comparisons of probability density functions (PDFs) of the observed and predicted GMs, the residual probabilistic scoring method (log-likelihood), and Sammon's maps. The latter is a visualization technique that allows a better understanding of the underlying epistemic uncertainty in GMM space. We put special emphasis on investigating how well the contributions from local geology are captured in the CSZ and two other subduction regions (i.e., Chile and Peru) to provide insights on the prediction of GMs in megathrust tectonic environments.

This project's main tasks are data collection, including GM records, earthquake and site metadata; the assessment of the performance of GMMs in different regions (i.e., CSZ, Chile, and Peru), and developing training materials for the next generation of earthquake engineers and engineering seismologists. The research is carried out collaboratively by three institutions: North Carolina State University (NC State), University of Concepción (UC), and University of Nevada, Reno (UNR).

RESULTS

Data Collection: GM data, including waveform information and site metadata, were collected at the study regions (i.e., the CSZ, Chile and Peru). Details associated with available data per region are provided below:

Data collection in the CSZ: Data for the CSZ were obtained from the NGA-Sub database (Mazzoni et al. 2022), including records in California, Washington, Oregon, and Canada (near Seattle). 26% of compiled earthquake ground motions in the CSZ were recorded in the state of Washington (Figure 1a). Figure 1b shows the record counts from 9 earthquakes in Washington state. The 2009 M_w 4.5 Kingston earthquake accounts for the largest number of records available for a single event. Figure 1c illustrates the range of the time-averaged shear wave velocity in the top 30 m ($V_{s,30}$) for recording stations in the CSZ. Most of the $V_{s,30}$ values range from 400 to 500 m/s, and 92% of the reported $V_{s,30}$ values were estimated using proxy-based models (Ahdi et al. 2022).

Figure 1. (a) Percentage of records in each selected sub-region within Cascadia, (b) number of records from each seismic event in the state of Washington, and (c) values of $V_{s,30}$ at recording stations in Cascadia (from both measurements and proxy-based models; after Ahdi et al. 2022).

Data Collection in Chile: The strong ground motion database used in this project corresponds to an update of the original database by Bastías and Montalva (2016). The new version contains 43,050 records from 6,679 earthquakes (Mw 4.0–8.8), recorded at 530 stations between 1985 and 2024. It includes extensive metadata, orientation-independent spectra, and site parameters (both measured and proxy-inferred V_{S30}). Flatfiles and waveform records are available through the DesignSafe repository (<https://doi.org/10.17603/ds2-6gyp-t353> ; Bastías et al., 2025).

Data Collection in Peru: Data for Peru were obtained from the NGA-Sub database (Mazzoni et al. 2022). A handful of additional site metadata (i.e., V_{S30}) were collected from a local source, the Servicio Nacional de Capacitación para la Industria de la Construcción (SENCICO).

Assessment of the performance of GMMs in different regions (CSZ, Chile, and Peru): Four GMMs were selected for this project. The Kuehn et al. (2020; 2023 KBCG20) model, which is a partially non-ergodic GMM, includes ground-motion scaling terms that are adjustable to accommodate differences among seven subduction-zone regions, including Cascadia and South America. The Parker et al. (2020; PSBAH20), model was formulated with global data but includes adjustment factors for Cascadia, southern and northern regions of South America. The Abrahamson and Gulerce (2020; 2022 AG20/AG22) model, which also includes region-specific models for Cascadia and South America. The AG20 Cascadia-specific model is applicable to distances of 800 km including the backarc region. Compared to KBCG20 and PSBAH20, the AG20 GMM has larger aleatory variability at short periods for the South America region (as well as for the Central America region and Japan). Finally, we also selected a Chile-specific GMM (i.e., Montalva et al. 2017; MBR17). Similar to the AG20 model, the MBR17 model selects the functional form by Abrahamson et al. (2016) because it provides a good fit to a subset of the data from the Chilean subduction zone.

To quantitatively evaluate the performance of GMMs, observed and predicted GMs were compared by calculating residuals using Eq. 1:

$$R_{ij} = \ln(Y_{ij}) - \ln(\hat{Y}_{ij}) \quad (1)$$

where Y_{ij} is the recorded intensity measure, IM (e.g., peak ground acceleration – PGA) for a site “i” given an event “j,” and \hat{Y}_{ij} is the GMM-based counterpart. Three approaches were used to evaluate the selected GMMs. First, we compared the PDF mean and standard deviation of the observed and predicted GMs, considering normal distributions as commonly assumed. The residuals were used to assess any systematic over or underprediction of GMs. Second, we estimated goodness-of-fit measures (e.g., mean and median of residuals normalized by their standard deviation) and a likelihood-based parameter to implement the probabilistic scoring method (Scherbaum et al. 2004). The likelihood-based approach results in a single

score for each period and GMM and can “quantify the model fit but also measure how well the underlying statistical model assumptions are met” (Scherbaum et al. 2004). Third, Sammon’s mapping techniques (e.g., Scherbaum et al. 2010) were used as a visualization method to map the uncertainty space represented by the distribution of GMMs.

Figure 2 shows residuals for pseudo-spectral accelerations obtained for CSZ, Chile and Peru, using the aforementioned GMMs. In Cascadia, 100 observations of the 2001 M_w 6.8 Nisqually earthquake were used to compute the residuals shown in Figures 2a and d. In contrast to the results from the Cascadia data, the KBCG20 model underpredicts Chilean ground motions ($\ln Y_{obs} > \ln Y_{pred}$) at short periods (0.01 and 0.1 s; see Figure 2b for residuals corresponding to 0.01 s in Chile). A similar behavior is observed for the PSBAH20 and AG20 models (not shown in Figure 2). At longer periods (1 and 3 s), KBCG20 mainly underpredicts Chilean GMs for softer sites (Figure 2e) but overpredicts for stiffer sites, whereas both PSBAH20 and AG20 tend to overpredict across all site classes. The Chile-specific model, MBR17, overpredicts for stiff sites ($V_{S30} > 600$ m/s) at 0.01, 0.1, and 1 s, while showing mean residuals closer to zero between 250 and 600 m/s. For the Peruvian data (Fig. 2c,f) residual analyses against available V_{S30} values also aim to identify any trends with the site scaling across different spectral periods. The scatter of residuals indicates some systematic trends visible at specific V_{S30} ranges, namely that at short oscillator periods (0.02 to 0.1 s), residuals are relatively unbiased and exhibit some clustering at higher V_{S30} , while at intermediate to long periods (~ 3 s), the residuals’ shift toward negative values, suggesting overprediction.

Figure 2. Variation of residuals with $V_{s,30}$ for (a) and (d) the 2001 M_w 6.8 Nisqually earthquake using the Kuehn et al. 2020 (KBCG20) model for pseudo-spectral accelerations (PSAs) at 0.01 and 1 s, respectively; (b) and (e), the Chilean dataset using KBCG20 model for PSAs at 0.01 and 1 s, respectively; and (c) and (f) the Peruvian dataset using the Parker et al. 2022 (PSHAB20) model for PSAs at 0.02 and 3 s, respectively.

Figure 3 presents the log-likelihood (LLH) scores for the residuals from selected GMMs as a function of oscillator period. The LLH score quantifies the agreement between observed and predicted GMs, with lower values (approaching 1 to 2) indicating a closer fit and higher values reflecting poorer agreement. In this computation, we followed the evaluation methodology outlined by McNamara et al. (2020). The LLH

scoring method quantifies the similarity between two continuous probability density functions (PDFs), $f(x)$ and $g(x)$. The LLH scoring method is defined using Eq. 2 (Beauval et al, 2012; Delavaud et al, 2009; McNamara et al, 2020) as follows:

$$LLH = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log_2(g(x_i)) \quad (2)$$

where model g is Gaussian (normal) distribution. As seen in Figure 3b, for the Chilean subduction zone, MBR17 consistently achieves the lowest LLH values (mean = 2.27 across the analyzed periods, with limited variability). This indicates that MBR17 provides the best fit for the observed data, demonstrating both accuracy and stability across the spectral range. AG20 and KBCG20 exhibit good performance up to 0.3 s, but their LLH values fluctuate between 0.3 and 5 s before increasing again in longer periods. Their best performance is observed for oscillator periods ranging from 3 to 5 s. PSBAH20 shows a good fit up to 5 s, but its LLH values increase toward values close to 4 at 10 s. These trends are summarized in Figure 3b. The variability of LLH values across models for the Chilean dataset suggests the convenience of adopting a logic-tree framework. MBR17 could be considered as a potential central or reference model given its stronger fit, while PSBAH20 and KBCG20 offer complementary perspectives to represent epistemic uncertainty. Although AG20 shows comparatively lower performance, it still provides useful insights that contribute to broadening the representation of model uncertainty.

For Peru (Figure 3c), PSBAH20 consistently yields the lowest and most stable LLH scores across the full spectral range, remaining close to 2, which suggests strong compatibility with the observed dataset. AG20 performs comparably well across periods up to 2 s but shows a gradual increase in LLH over longer periods. This increase implies a reduced predictive accuracy for long-period ground motions. In contrast, KBCG20 demonstrates relatively higher LLH values across periods, except around 1 s, and a pronounced increase at periods longer than 3 s. These findings indicate that the PSBAH20 model can be adopted to estimate ground motions in Peru, while AG20 and particularly KBCG20 exhibit notable limitations in capturing long-period response characteristics for this region. This outcome aligns with the approach emphasized in McNamara et al. (2020), where LLH was used as a probabilistic measure to rank and weight GMMs based on their ability to reproduce recorded ground motions.

Using the limited data from the Nisqually earthquake, we observe that in the short period range (i.e., less than 1 second), KBCG20 model shows the lowest LLH score (Figure 3a), and the PSBAH20 model shows the highest LLH score. Then, all GMMs show similar LLH score between 1.5 to 2 seconds. AG22 (adjusted) provide LLH scores closer to 2 across most periods for the CSZ data; but larger scatter is observed.

Figure 3. Log-Likelihood scoring method in three regions: (a) Cascadia, (b) Chile, and (c) Peru. Note that AG20 and AG22 models refer to the same GMM. The AG20 model corresponds to an earlier publication as a PEER report.

Figure 4 presents the dimensionality reductions of the residuals from the selected predictive models using Sammon maps. These maps allow the spatial positioning in a low-dimensional space (N=2) of the relative

proximity or separation among models within the study domain. Furthermore, they provide a qualitative means to assess whether the predictive models represent the same epistemic uncertainty. As seen in Fig. 4, at spectral periods of 0.01, 0.1, and 3 s, each predictive model is in a different quadrant with respect to the mean residuals (calculated for the Chilean data), supporting the rationale for employing all models within a logic-tree framework. At 1 s, the KBCG20 and AG20 models appear close to each other in the Cartesian analysis space. It is also observed that the MBR17 model is generally more distant from the rest, which is reasonable given that it was developed using a different database and calibration methodology compared to the NGA-Sub models.

Figure 4. Sammon's mapping applied for oscillator periods (T): (a) 0.01 s, (b) 1 s, and (c) 3 s and selected NGA-Sub GMMs and a Chile-specific GMM.

Overall, we find consistent patterns in the residuals, with trends at long periods being generally better captured, while short distances and short periods remaining a challenge. The lack of available subsurface characterization, particularly in the CSZ and Peru limits more robust assessments of how well site effects are captured by existing GMMs. More data should be collected in these regions, especially at recording ground motion stations.

Training the next generation of earthquake engineers and engineering seismologists: three graduate students have been actively involved in this project. PI Cabas created a video on the fundamentals of site response that will soon be shared and translated to Spanish on the E2SCALA website. Moreover, two graduate students were supported by this project to attend the 2025 SSA Annual Meeting.

FUTURE WORK

Further curation of the compiled data for estimating the performance of GMMs in each region will take place along with the creation of Jupyter notebooks (i.e., for the residual analysis, LLH score estimation, and Sammon's mapping) to share with the broader community. These materials will be shared as educational materials on the E²SCALA website. In addition, the team is preparing a conference paper for the 13th National Conference on Earthquake Engineering, in Portland, Oregon on July 13 - 17 2026.

PRESENTATIONS AND OTHER PRODUCTS

- An Updated Review of Ground Motion Flatfiles in the Chilean Subduction Zone ([Bastias et al. SSA 2025](#))
- Advancing Seismic Site Response: Numerical Assessment of Vs Gradient and Sv-Wave Propagation ([Katuwal and Pretell SSA 2025](#))
- Youtube [video](#) on Site Response Analysis by PI Cabas, which will also be hosted (the Spanish version) on the E2SCALA website in the near future (<https://youtu.be/UuOz364pkTg?si=xRt6k-6eQPqL0Cdi>).

REFERENCES

- Abrahamson, N., Gregor, N., & Addo, K. (2016). BC Hydro ground motion prediction equations for subduction earthquakes. *Earthquake Spectra*, 32(1), 23–44.
- Abrahamson, N., & Gülerce, Z. (2020). Regionalized ground-motion models for subduction earthquakes based on the NGA-SUB database. *Report 2020/05*. Berkeley, CA: Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center, University of California, Berkeley
- Abrahamson, N. A., & Gülerce, Z. (2022). Summary of the Abrahamson and Gülerce NGA-SUB ground-motion model for subduction earthquakes. *Earthquake Spectra*, 38(4), 2638–2681. <https://doi.org/10.1177/87552930221114374>
- Bastías, N., & Montalva, G. A. (2016). Chile strong ground motion flatfile. *Earthquake Spectra*, 32(4), 2549-2566.
- Beauval, C., Tasan, H., Laurendeau, A., Delavaud, E., Cotton, F., Gueguen, P., & Kuehn, N. (2012). On the Testing of Ground-Motion Prediction Equations against Small-Magnitude Data. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 102(5), 1994–2007. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0120110271>
- Delavaud, E., Scherbaum, F., Kuehn, N., & Riggelsen, C. (2009). Information-Theoretic Selection of Ground-Motion Prediction Equations for Seismic Hazard Analysis: An Applicability Study Using Californian Data. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 99(6), 3248–3263. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0120090055>
- Kuehn, N., Bozorgnia, Y., Campbell, K., & Gregor, N. (2020). Partially Non-Ergodic Ground-Motion Model for Subduction Regions using the NGA Subduction Database (PEER Reports) [PEER Reports]. Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center, University of California, Berkeley, CA. <https://doi.org/10.55461/NZZW1930>
- Kuehn, N. M., Bozorgnia, Y., Campbell, K. W., & Gregor, N. (2023). A regionalized partially nonergodic ground-motion model for subduction earthquakes using the NGA-Sub database. *Earthquake Spectra*, 39(3), 1625-1657.
- McNamara, D. E., Wolin, E., Powers, P. M., Shumway, A. M., Moschetti, M. P., Rekoske, J., Thompson, E. M., Mueller, C. S., & Petersen, M. D. (2020). Evaluation of Ground-Motion Models for U.S. Geological Survey Seismic Hazard Models: 2018 Anchorage, Alaska, Mw 7.1 Subduction Zone Earthquake Sequence. *Seismological Research Letters*, 91(1), 183–194. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220190188>
- Montalva, G. A., Bastías, N., & Rodriguez-Marek, A. (2017). Ground-Motion Prediction Equation for the Chilean Subduction Zone. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 107(2), 901–911. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0120160221>
- Parker, G. A., Stewart, J. P., Boore, D. M., Atkinson, G. M., & Hassani, B. (2022). NGA-subduction global ground motion models with regional adjustment factors. *Earthquake Spectra*, 38(1), 456–493. <https://doi.org/10.1177/87552930211034889>
- Sammon, J. W. (1969). A Nonlinear Mapping for Data Structure Analysis. *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, C-18(5), 401–409. <https://doi.org/10.1109/T-C.1969.222678>

- Scherbaum, F., Delavaud, E., & Riggelsen, C. (2009). Model Selection in Seismic Hazard Analysis: An Information-Theoretic Perspective. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 99(6), 3234–3247. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0120080347>
- Scherbaum, F., Kuehn, N. M., Ohrnberger, M., & Koehler, A. (2010). Exploring the Proximity of Ground-Motion Models Using High-Dimensional Visualization Techniques. *Earthquake Spectra*, 26(4), 1117–1138. <https://doi.org/10.1193/1.3478697>